

Visible light irradiate photocatalytic degradation of textile dye with a newly developed photocatalyst MBIR Dowex 11

R. C. Meena*, R. S. Sindal and Munesh

Photochemistry Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Jai Narain Vyas University, Jodhpur-342 001, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : rcmeena007@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received online 11 April 2012, revised 16 May 2012, accepted 29 May 2012

Abstract : Azo dye acid orange 12 creates environment pollution problems by releasing toxic and potential carcinogenic substance in the aqueous phase. Visible light photocatalytic degradation of acid orange 12 was carried out by employing heterogeneous photocatalyst methylene blue immobilized resin (MBIR) Dowex 11. Photodegradation efficiency was small when the photolysis was carried out in the absence of MBIR Dowex 11, and it was also negligible in the absence of UV light. The optimum values of different parameters which influence the degradation of azo dye such as catalyst dose, concentration of dye, pH of the solution, light intensity and radical quencher was systematically studied. The dye solution could be completely decolorized and effectively mineralized, with average removal efficiency larger than 95% for a reaction time 160 min. Photocatalytic degradation of the dyes follows pseudo-first order kinetics. CO₂ and H₂O are obtained of simple mineralize products.

Keywords : Photodegradation, immobilization, photocatalyst, acid orange 12, removal efficiency, MBIR Dowex 11.

Introduction

The textile effluents discharge causes serious stress on natural water bodies and land in the surrounding areas. High values of COD and BOD, presence of particulate matter and sediments which are dark in color leading to turbidity that causes depletion of dissolved oxygen, which has direct effect on the marine ecological system and indirect on human metabolic system. In recent years an alternative to conventional methods is advance oxidation process (AOPs) based on the formation of very reactive species such as hydroxyl radicals which is produced by means of chemical, photochemical, photocatalytic reaction. That easily and non selectively, oxidizes a broad range of organic effluents¹⁻⁴. AOPs such as catalytic oxidation using photo-Fenton, Fenton and visible/solar light system and TiO₂ photocatalysis⁵⁻⁷. The problem connected with the above processes involves separation and treatment of the homogenous mixture from the suspension. In order to solve this problem, supported photocatalyst has been developed^{8,9}. In particular, titanium powder has been immobilized on supports transparent to UV/Vis radiation¹⁰⁻¹². Unfortunately, the surface area of active catalyst exposed to solution is lower in supported systems in

suspended systems, reducing the catalytic activity. TiO₂ is the most widely used catalyst, mainly because of its photo stability, low cost and non toxicity and insoluble in water under most environmental conditions¹³. But this technology has not yet been successfully commercialized in past because of problems connected to the separation of TiO₂ particles from suspension. To solve this problem, supported photocatalyst has been developed¹⁴⁻¹⁷. Photodegradation of azo dyes by chitosan capped CdS composite nanoparticles and in aqueous phase nanophotocatalysts^{18,19}. Photocatalytic and combined anaerobic photocatalytic treatment of textile dyes^{20,21}. The purpose of doping (modeling) of metal ions and photosensitization by various colored organic and inorganic compounds in order to extend the photo response of large band gap semiconductors into visible region to use them for the degradation of colored organic pollutants^{22,23}. Visible light sensitive photocatalyst have been developed by Meena *et al.*^{24,25}. The development of visible light photocatalyst is an impressive task in order to utilize the solar energy effectively. Keeping in view the above, the main objective of the present work is to seek attention of researchers towards utilization of visible light for degra-

dition of azo dye Acid orange 12 by recently developed photocatalyst (MBIR) Dowex 11.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Acid orange 12	= Loba (Loba Chemicals India)
IUPAC Name	= 1-Phenylazo-2-naphthol-6-sulfonic acid sodium salt
Molecular formula	= C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ NaO ₄ S
Molecular weight	= 350.32
Solubility	= Soluble in water
Appearance	= Orange
λ_{\max}	= 482 nm
Class	= Azo

We prepared photocatalyst by following materials Dowex 11 Resin 20–50 mesh (Sisco Chemicals, Mumbai India). Methylene blue hydrates for microscopy (Loba Chemicals India). For immobilization we prepare approximately M/1000 concentration solution of methylene blue in double distilled water and add Dowex 11 resin in this solution and shake well for immobilization of pores of resin. All the process carried out in dark place. Then filter prepared resin from solution, wash this resin by double distilled water twice and used it as photocatalyst. Photochemical degradation experiments were carried out in glass reactor which containing solution of Acid orange 12 dye (Fig. 1) and photocatalyst. Solution of reactor is continuously stirred by magnetic stirrer during the experiment. The solution is illuminated by halogen lamp (Philips, India) above the reactor which emitted irradiation

Fig. 1. Structure of dye Acid Orange 12.

tion comparable to visible light shown in Fig. 2. The intensity was measured by photometer (IL1400A). The lamp was surrounded with aluminium reflector in order to avoid loss of irradiation. pH of the solution was monitored by Fisher Scientific Acumen 50. The mechanism of the photodegradation process under UV-Visible light illumination involves an electron excitation and generation of very active oxygenated species that attack the dye molecules leading to photodegradation.

We suck out 10 ml solution of reaction mixture with the help of a syringe at 20 min time interval, and filtered the catalyst particles through Millipore syringe and change in concentration of dye solution is measured simply by Shimadzu-1600 UV/Visible spectrophotometer at $\lambda_{\max} = 482$ nm. Calculate the removal efficiency (X) of dye solution by this equation.

$$X = (C_i - C_t / C_i)$$

where, C_i and C_t are optical densities of dye solution at initial time and at time t respectively.

Results and discussion

Kinetic study :

Photocatalytic degradation of Acid orange 12 was observed at $\lambda_{\max} = 482$ nm. The optimum condition was obtained at initial dye concentration : 40 mg/L, catalyst loading : 2 g/100 ml, solution volume : 100 ml, light intensity : 10.4 mW cm⁻², pH : 7.5 and temperature : 303 K. The plot of removal efficiency versus exposure time is a straight line (Fig. 3). This indicates that the photocatalytic degradation of Acid orange 12 follows pseudo-first order kinetics²⁶⁻²⁸ according to Langmuir-Hinshelwood model. The rate constant (K) for the reaction was determined using the expression. Rate = K [AO 12] K = 2.303 × slope. The rate constant for this reaction is K = 2.02 × 10⁻² min⁻¹.

Fig. 2. Experimental set-up of photochemical reaction chamber.

Fig. 3. Kinetic study for Acid Orange 12 photocatalyst system (initial dye concentration : 40 mg/L, pH : 7.5, catalyst loading : 2 g/100 ml, solution volume : 100 ml, light intensity : 10.4 mW cm⁻²).

FT-IR analysis :

The FTIR spectra analysis was employed by Spectro Jasco Corp./IR-610 over the range 599.7532–4000.605 cm⁻¹ using KBr pallets. The IR spectrum of Dowex-11 resin (pure) show peaks in the region 3100–2950 cm⁻¹ and 1600–1450 cm⁻¹ is attribute to =C–H stretching vibration and aromatic –C=C– stretching vibration shown in Fig. 4. The FTIR spectra of MBIR Dowex-11 show peaks in the region 3100–2950 cm⁻¹ and 1600–1450 cm⁻¹ is attribute to =C–H stretching vibration and aromatic –C=C– stretching vibration, and another two peaks in the region 3650–3400 cm⁻¹ and 1550–1510 cm⁻¹ due to >N–H stretching vibration and N–H bending. These

peaks arise due to immobilization of pores of resin with methylene blue dye shown in Fig. 5.

Effect of catalyst :

The amount of the photocatalyst is most important parameter that affects the rate of photocatalytic degradation. We observe the effect of variation in the amount of photocatalyst from 1.0 to 3.0 g/100 ml and concentration of dye 40 mg/L, at constant pH 7.5 and light intensity 10.4 mW cm⁻². Increase the amount of catalyst rate of degradation also increase due to availability of more catalyst surface area for absorption of quanta and interaction of molecules of reaction mixture with catalyst, resultant number of holes, hydroxyl radicals and super oxide ions (O₂⁻) are increase. These are principle oxidizing intermediate in advance oxidation process resultant increases degradation efficiency. Effect of catalyst loading on removal efficiency shown in Fig. 6.

Effect of initial dye concentration :

The effect of initial dye concentration on the degradation efficiency was studied by varying the concentration from 10 mg/L to 70 mg/L at constant photocatalyst (2 g/100 ml) the results are shown in Fig. 7. The concentration of dye increases the rate of degradation decreases. This effect arises due to the surface area of catalyst is fixed so as the concentration of dye increases rate of degradation decreases because limited number of dye molecules attached at the active site of the catalyst and remaining dye molecules persist in solution until earlier attached molecule are degraded and number of active site

Fig. 4. FTIR spectra of Dowex 11 (pure) resin.

Fig. 5. FTIR spectra of methylene blue immobilized resin Dowex 11.

of catalyst also decreases due to less availability of photons for excitation of catalyst molecules. At higher concentration number of dye molecules also high so more will be the competition between the dye molecules for attachment to active site of catalyst and resultant reduce

the rate of degradation.

Effect of pH :

We observe effect of pH on rate of degradation efficiency of dye molecules is very interesting. The results

Fig. 6. Effect of catalyst loading on removal efficiency (initial dye concentration : 40 mg/L, temperature : 303 K, solution volume : 100 ml, pH 7.5, light intensity : 10.4 mW cm⁻²).

Fig. 7. Effect of initial dye concentration on removal efficiency (temperature : 303 K, catalyst loading : 2 g/100 ml, solution volume : 100 ml, pH 7.5, light intensity : 10.4 mW cm⁻²).

show that rate of degradation is very low in high acidic pH range lower than pH 3.5. As well as pH increases rate of degradation also increases when pH reaches to basic range the rate of degradation increases fast, in pH range 7.5 to 9 very good rate of degradation. On further increase pH the rate of degradation also start to decrease after pH range 10 or above rate of degradation is less and continually decreases as pH increases. So we conclude

that rate of degradation in basic medium is higher than acidic medium. The increase in rate of photocatalytic degradation may be due to more availability of ⁻OH ions in pH range 7.5 to 9 will generate more •OH radicals by combining with the holes which are formed due to electronic excitation in catalyst. Formation of hydroxyl radicals is more responsible for the photocatalytic degradation than super oxide ions (O₂⁻). Graphical representation of pH effect on removal efficiency shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. Effect of pH on removal efficiency (initial dye concentration : 40 mg/L, temperature : 303 K, catalyst loading : 2 g/100 ml, solution volume : 100 ml, light intensity : 10.4 mW cm⁻²).

Effect of light intensity :

Light intensity increases the rate of degradation of dye molecules also increases upto some extent after it no change observe in rate of degradation. The light intensity increases number of photons increases to reach the catalyst surface, so number of excited catalyst molecules increases and resultant increase the hydroxyl radicals and super oxide ions (O₂⁻) and rate of degradation of dye molecules increase. We observe that after some extent of increase in light intensity there is no effect on rate of degradation on further increases in light intensity. This may cause that maximum number of photons which required for excitation are available in fix range irradiating light intensity after it, if we further increase light intensity no any considerable change observed in rate of degradation because there is no requirement of more photons

for excitation. Because all catalyst molecules become active (excited) in fix light intensity range after it we increase light intensity to any range, the rate of degradation remains unchanged. Effect of light intensity on removal efficiency is shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9. Effect of variation of light intensity on removal efficiency (initial dye concentration : 40 mg/L, temperature : 303 K, catalyst loading : 2 g/100 ml, solution volume : 100 ml, pH 7.5).

Fig. 10. Effect of radical quencher on removal efficiency (initial dye concentration : 40 mg/L, temperature : 303 K, catalyst loading : 2 g/100 ml, solution volume : 100 ml, pH 7.5, light intensity : 10.4 mW cm⁻²).

Effect of variation in radical quencher :

The oxidative intermediate species such as super oxide ions and hydroxyl radicals under photocatalytic conditions and their role in the dye degradation process has been investigated indirectly with the use of appropriate quenchers of these species. As it was observed from the experiment that degradation rate of Acid orange 12 were decreases as the ratio of the concentration of propanol increases from 10 : 100 to 20 : 100. Alcohols such as ethanol and propanol are commonly used to quench hydroxyl radicals. So as the ratio of propanol in the dye solution was increases the rate of degradation decreased. This enables us to draw the conclusion that small amount of propanol inhibits the photocatalytic degradation. The effect of radical quencher on photocatalytic activity is graphically represented in Fig. 10.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the CSIR, New Delhi for financial support through JRF Sanction No. 09/098(0094)/2010 EMR-I and Head of the Department for providing necessary facilities.

References

1. N. Daneshver, S. Aber and F. Hosseinzadeh, *J. Global NEST*, 2008, **10**, 16.
2. M. Muruganandham and M. Swaminathan, *Dyes Pigment*, 2007, **72**, 137.
3. P. R. Gogate and A. R. Pandit, *Adv. Environ. Res.*, 2004, **8**, 501.
4. W. S. Kuo and P. H. Ho, *Chemosphere*, 2001, **45**, 77.
5. M. S. Lucas and J. A. Peres, *Dyes and Pigment*, 2006, **71**, 235.
6. S. Wang, *Dye and Pigment*, 2008, **76**, 714.
7. A. Kumar, M. Paliwal, R. Ameta and S. C. Ameta, *J. Iran Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **5**, 346.
8. H. Lachheb, E. Puzenat, A. Houas, M. Ksibi, E. Elaloui, C. Guillard and J. M. Hermann, *Appl. Catal. B : Environ.*, 2002, **39**, 75.
9. C. M. Ling, A. R. Muhamed and S. Bhatia, *Chemosphere*, 2004, **57**, 547.
10. A. R. Khataee, M. N. Pons and O. Zahraa, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2009, **168**, 451.
11. L. Tatti, D. Niego, F. Rota, P. Bruzzi, A. Moroni, I. R. Bellobono, M. Bonardi, M. Bianchi and H. Muntau, *Chemosphere*, 1997, **34**, 41.

12. A. Rachel, M. Subrahmanyam and P. Boule, *Appl. Catal. B : Environ.*, 2002, **37**, 301.
13. P. A. Carneiro, M. E. Osugi, J. J. Sene, M. A. Anderson and M. V. B. Zanoni, *Electrochem. Acta*, 2004, **49**, 3807.
14. A. R. Khataee and M. B. Kasiri, *J. Mole. Catal. A : Chem.*, 2010, **328**, 8.
15. K. Tanaka, K. Padermpole and T. Hisanaga, *Water Res.*, 2000, **7**, 327.
16. C. G. Da Silva and J. L. Faria, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 2003, **155**, 133.
17. S. A. Abo-Farha, *J. Am. Sci.*, 2010, **6**, 130.
18. Jiang Ru, Huayue Zhu, Xiaodong Li and Ling Xiao, *J. Chem. Engg.*, 2009, **152**, 537.
19. S. K. Kansal, A. H. Ali and S. Kapoor, *Desalination*, 2010, **259**, 147.
20. F. Harrelkas, A. Paulo, M. M. Alves, L. El Khadir, O. Zahraa, M. N. Pons and F. P. vander Zee, *Chemosphere*, 2008, **72**, 1816.
21. D. Mendez-Pazet, F. Omil and J. M. Iema, *Wat. Res.*, 2005, **39**, 771.
22. K. Wilke and H. D. Breuer, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A : Chem.*, 1999, **121**, 49.
23. I. H. Tseng, W. C. Chang and J. C. S. Wu, *Appl. Catal. B : Environ.*, 2002, **37**, 37.
24. R. C. Meena and Rambabu Pachwarya, *J. Scient. Ind. Res.*, 2009, **68**, 730.
25. R. C. Meena, Rambabu Pachwarya, Vijay Kumar Meena and Shakuntala Arya, *Am. J. Environ. Sci.*, 2009, **5**, 444.
26. M. A. Behnajady, N. Modirshahla and R. Hamzavi, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2006, **133**, 226.
27. M. Faisal, M. Abu Tariq and M. Muneer, *Dye Pigment*, 2007, **72**, 233.
28. H. Ted Chang, Nan-Min Wu and Faqing Zhu, *Wat. Res.*, 2000, **34**, 407.

